

Rigorous Mathematical Thinking Level Relational Abstract in Solve Non-routine Problems of Integral Broad Materials

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Article Info	Abstract
<p>Article History</p> <p>Received: April 05, 2021</p> <p>Accepted: June 03, 2021</p> <hr/> <p>Keywords: Cognitive function, Decision making, Mental processes, Qualitative review, Problem-solving</p> <p>DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4897788</p>	<p><i>The use of knowledge in thinking is necessary to solve mathematical problems. It involves cognitive function as a mental process for specific actions necessary to directly describe abstraction and generalization. There are three levels of cognitive function in Strict Mathematical Thinking: level 1 is qualitative thinking, level 2 is quantitative review with precision, and 3 is relational abstract thinking. This study aims to determine the description of high school students' strict math thinking skills at a conceptual relational level. This study used a qualitative descriptive approach involving five students who qualified for the 1st and 2nd preliminary round at the provincial mathematics Olympiad. Data collection techniques used written tests, interviews, as well as documentation, and then analyzed using comparison techniques. Furthermore, the data validity was carried out using data triangulation based on cognitive function. The results showed that out of 5 subjects, only one problem was at the level of relational abstract thinking. Abstract relational thinking is a cognitive function associated with mental processes in decision making based on a good overall relationship. At this level, students can integrate processes on quantity and accuracy into a logical order</i></p>

Introduction

Mathematics and its concepts are present in a diverse relationships of all processes in engineering, in theoretical constructs applied to descriptions and phenomenological representations, and in structuring physical space in which the professionals of these areas operate (Santos *et al.*, 2020). Mathematical competencies can be fostered as part of thinking processes that understand problematic situations and information in different contexts (Quezada, 2020). In general, mathematical disciplines and linear algebra, in particular, require the development of problem-solving skills (Fadiawati, Diawati and Syamsuri, 2020). Meanwhile, students' assimilation of the domain cannot be regarded as profound and practical (E.M.Vorob'ev, 2012). Also, one of the materials in mathematics is integral (Sharzadin *et al.*, 2019). In addition, students' critical understanding is relatively low because they often have challenges in solving essential questions.

Ramdani stated that math national test in 2010 from 879 high school students showed their average capability on integral concepts was lower than 50% compared to other high schools (Ramdani, 2012). Participants of the Mathematics Olympiad, deal with non-routine questions usually because they have superior abilities compared to other students. This opinion is in line with Cress *et al.*, that talented students can have high achievement because of their excellent skills (Cress *et al.*, 2018). Also, students need to utilize their knowledge for thinking before engaging in mental actions through their brains' understanding to solve mathematical problems (Sundawan, Irmawan and Sulaiman, 2019). When they cannot understand the question, they will have some cognitive issues in its interpretation, and in thinking, natural cognitive functions are involved (Rajasulochana and Senthil Ganesh, 2019). Cognitive functions are mental processes with some special meanings conveyed for specific thinking actions, which are required to directly describe abstractions and generalizations (Maharani *et al.*, 2019).

For rigorous mathematical thinking, three levels of cognitive function are required: level 1 is qualitative review, level 2 is quantitative thinking with accuracy, and 3 is abstract relational thinking (Kinard, 2006). These define general mental processes of cognitive skills' to a higher mathematical knowledge level (Cai *et al.*, 2019). Students realize the importance of accuracy as the base of proving in rigorous mathematical thinking (Suparmi *et al.*, 2017). Also, they can apply the axioms, theorems, definitions, and right mathematical concepts to strengthen their proving (Vázquez *et al.*, 2018). According to mathematical systems concepts, students comprehend the correlation between undefined forms (Yunita, Maharani and Sulaiman, 2019). Meanwhile, the RMT aims to grow and apply a deep mathematical and conceptual understanding that students have intellectual perseverance, critical thinking (Saputro *et al.*, 2020), and in-depth knowledge.

Abstract relational thinking is the third level of cognitive function in RMT, which is the highest. According to Yunita [14], abstract relational thinking is a cognitive function related to mental processes in decision making based on overall correlations that make sense. At this level, students can integrate some processes related to quantity and accuracy into a series of abstract relational logic and thought. Also, relational thinking can be connected to meaningful learning, and students can entirely comprehend the concepts they learn to apply these concepts in relevant mathematical problems.

According to Fitriyani, there are some cognitive functions used in abstract relational thinking, they are: (1) activating previous mathematical knowledge, (2) providing mathematical and logical evidence, (3) articulating logical-mathematical situation, (4) defining the problem, (5) hypothetical thinking, (6) inferential thinking, (7) projecting and restructuring the correlation, (8) forming proportional quantitative correlation, (9) mathematical inductive thinking, (10) mathematical deductive thinking, (11) mathematical relational thinking, and (12) elaborating mathematical activity through cognitive categories (Fitriyani, 2011).

Mathematical literacy is a critical ability to support students' skills (Veen *et al.*, 2019), which are used in everyday life (Quezada, 2020). The importance of competencies in the 21st century has given rise to the appearance of essential topics related to ensuring a necessary knowledge database for children and young people to be competent in modern and future societies (Gualiza, Naelga and Blanco, 2017).

This study aims to find a description of rigorous mathematical thinking skills at an abstract relational level of Mathematical Olympiad student participants in solving non-routine questions. The results can be some points of consideration for the Olympiad coaches and schools to send subjects to join or participate at the City, Provincial, National, and International level.

Method

This is a qualitative study with descriptive methods. The subjects are five high school students who passed the preliminary round 1 and 2 at the Provincial Olympiad at the Faculty of Mathematics and Natural Sciences, University of SwadayaGunungJati. Furthermore, the instrument used was a rigorous mathematical thinking ability test (written test). Also, data triangulation was used for validity, where the techniques used for data collection were written tests, interviews, and documentation. The data analysis technique used a fixed comparison method, including reduction, categorization, synthesis, and conclusion.

Results and Discussion

Based on the analysis process, it was found that subjects do not fully apply the cognitive function of the RMT. However, this topic is stated to reach that level by using some of the RMT cognitive functions. The instruments used to conduct the Rigorous Mathematical Thinking (RMT) test can be seen in table 1 and figure 1.

Table 1. RMT Test Results

No.	Questions	Results
1.	Please solve the following problem based on your pure-reasoning! Prove that the subdivision of the surface wide of a sphere with radius a which is placed between two paralleled planes separated each other as far as h ($h < 2a$) is $2\pi ah$ and then show that if several cylindric forms are covered inside the sphere, those two paralleled flat planes with the cylinder area would be delimitating the regions with the same wide on the sphere cylinder form. After we prove and show the given statement, let us take that the described sphere building as earth with radius 4000 mil and then seen in figure 1.	1. The subject can write that the distance between the two parallel fields is h . He can also show and give the name of the element in a spherical image in the form of a radius, and he can explain that the diameter is equal to twice the radius.
2.	Based on figure 1, how wide the cover of S polar above 75° paralleled and how large the sphere-segment volume would	2. $S = \rho \cos \varphi$ $S = \rho \cos 75^\circ$

have occurred if the entire S plane points are connected to the line fragments toward the earth's center?

Figure 1. The sphere building

Here are the descriptions of the five subjects' RMT ability.

1. Subject 1 has used several cognitive functions at level 1 RMT, which means issue 1 can reach level 1 of qualitative thinking, but some cognitive functions have not been shown or performed. Also, subject has not used the cognitive tasks of rigorous mathematical thinking at level 2 and 3 to solve non-routine maths problems. Therefore, because the subject is still in tenth grade, some theories has not been mastered. Subject 1 RMT ability can be seen in table 2.

Table 2. Subject' Use of Cognitive Function Level 1, Qualitative Thinking

Cognitive Functions	Results/Answers
Labeling	The subject can write that the distance between two parallel fields is h . Subject can also show and give the name of element in a spherical image in the form of a radius. Furthermore, subject can explain that the diameter is equal to twice the radius.
Visualizing	The subject can explain a sphere cut by two parallel fields with $h < 2a$ distance and explain parts of the globe cut by two similar areas. Nevertheless, for the drawing phase, the subject still needs guidance in advance.
Comparing, searching systematically to gather precise and complete information, using more than one source of information.	The subject's skills cannot be seen at these functions.
Encoding	The subject can show that the distance between two parallel fields is $h < 2a$.

Cognitive Functions	Results/Answers
Decoding	The subject can explain why the distance between the two parallel fields is $h < 2a$.

2. Subject 2 has performed some cognitive functions at level 3 RMT, which means issue 2 can reach level 3 of abstract relational thinking. But at level 3, there are some cognitive functions that was not performed. Subject 2 RMT ability can be seen in table 3.

Table 3. Subject' Use of Cognitive Function Level 1, Qualitative Thinking

Cognitive Functions	Results/Answers
Labeling	The subject can write that distance between two parallel fields is h . The subject can also show and give the name of an element in a spherical image in the form of a radius. Furthermore, subject can explain that the diameter is equal to twice the radius.
Visualizing	The subject can explain a sphere cut by two parallel planes with $h < 2a$ distance and explain parts of the globe cut by two similar fields. Nevertheless, the subject makes a mistake thinking that the two parallel areas divide the sphere into half.
Comparing, searching systematically to gather precise and complete information.	The subject's skill cannot be seen at these functions.
Using more than one source of information.	The subject used the concept of limits and angles to find the sphere's area and used the circle equation to determine the function $f(x)$.
Encoding	The subject can show that the distance between the two parallel fields is $h < 2a$.
Decoding	The subject can show why the distance between the two parallel fields is $h < 2a$.

3. Subject 3 has shown some cognitive functions at level 1 RMT, and it means that the subject has reached level 1 of qualitative thinking. But at this level, there are cognitive functions that has not been performed. Also, the subject has not applied cognitive function of mathematical thinking rigor at level 2 and 3 to demonstrate how non-routine math problems were solved. Because the subject is still in eleventh grade, mathematical theory knowledge has not been fully trained. Subject 3 RMT ability can be seen in table 4.

Table 4. Subject' Use of Cognitive Function Level 1, Qualitative Thinking

Cognitive Functions	Results/Answers
Labeling	The subject can write that the distance between two parallel fields is h . Furthermore, the subject can also show and give the name of an element in a spherical image in the form of a radius, and can explain that the diameter is equal to twice the radius.
Visualizing	The subject can visualize two parallel fields that cut the sphere at a distance less than its diameter. But for the drawing stage, the issue still needs guidance in advance.
Encoding	The subject can mention the radius object in a sphere with the symbol a .
Decoding	The subject can find the meaning of symbol h , which is the distance of two parallel fields.
Comparing, searching systematically to gather precise and complete	The subject's skill cannot be seen at these functions.

Cognitive Functions	Results/Answers
information, using more than one source of information.	

4. Subject 4 has performed some cognitive functions at level 1 RMT, which means that level 1 of qualitative thinking can be reached. But at level 1, there are mental functions that has not been shown. The issue has not also applied the cognitive function of rigorous mathematical thinking at level 2 and 3 in solving non-routine math problems. Because the subject is still in tenth grade, therefore mathematical theory knowledge is incomplete. Subject 4 RMT ability can be seen in table 5.

Table 5. Subject' Use of Cognitive Function Level 1, Qualitative Thinking

Cognitive Functions	Results/Answers
Labeling	The subject can write that the sphere radius is a and the distance between two parallel fields is h .
Visualizing	The subject can explain the sphere with radius a , but cannot describe the globe cut by two parallel fields with $h < 2a$ distance.
Comparing and searching systematically to gather precise and complete information, using more than one source of information, encoding, and decoding.	The subject's skill cannot be seen at these functions.

5. Subject 5 has applied some cognitive functions at level 1 RMT, which means that level 1 of qualitative thinking can be reached. But at level 1, there are mental functions that was not shown. Furthermore, the issue has not applied cognitive function of rigorous mathematical thinking at level 2 and 3 in solving non-routine math questions. Because the subject is still a tenth grader, knowledge about mathematical theories has not been fully completed. Subject 5 RMT ability can be seen in table 6.

Table 6. Subject' Use of Cognitive Function Level 1, Qualitative Thinking

Cognitive Functions	Results/Answers
Labeling	The subject can write that the sphere radius is a and the distance between two parallel fields is h .
Visualizing	The subject can explain the sphere with radius but cannot describe the globe cut by two parallel fields with $h < 2a$ distance.
Comparing and searching systematically to gather precise and complete information, using more than one information source: encoding and decoding.	The subject's skill cannot be seen at these functions.

RMT is a learning approach based on two main theories: the psychological theory of Vygotsky and the learning theory from Feuerstein. This approach emphasizes the interaction and mediation between teachers and students, resulting in a good understanding of the presented material (Kinard, 2006). The Vygotsky's psychological theory stated that the use of media in learning can help students integrate cognitive function with basic concepts that can support mathematical generalization and abstraction (Smagorinsky, 2011). The media can be in form of symbols, tables, diagrams, drawings, maps, graphs, and coding (Pakdaman-savoji and Nesbit, 2019). Also, the media is expected to bridge students' understanding of a problem and is a new experience obtained (Jarudin, Ibrahim and Muslim, 2020).

The RMT can be one of the alternative learning approaches to help students associate their previous knowledge with the problems at hand and develop new ideas in finding the right solutions to solve math problems (Hidayat,

Nurlaelah and Dahlan, 2017). Also, RMT makes it possible to produce digital books to illustrate abstract representations to build understanding and generate conceptualization of coherent and logical ideas to facilitate problem-solving (Meilantifa and Budiarto, 2018).

Conclusion

Based on the results and discussion of this study after written tests, interviews, and documentation, it was shown that out of the five subjects, only one can achieve RMT level 3 and abstract relational thinking. Although point two has not used all cognitive functions of grade 3, and topic 3 has used several cognitive tasks of level 3. Furthermore, the subject was confused with the English questions. Also, results can be points of consideration for the Mathematical coaches to send subjects to join Olympiad at City, Provincial, National, and International level. Nevertheless, the coaches should provide more various questions to support the participants' RMT development.

This study is only limited to RMT as conceptual mastery, and it is necessary to explore the impact of MRT on problem-solving and other cognitive skills.

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